

To Study the Impact of Homeschooling on Students Achievements - A Simple Literature Review

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Running head: To Study the Impact of Homeschooling

Abstract: This article provides an analysis of the literature review of the impact of Homeschooling on student's achievement in a science subject. In the analysis of the review, most of the peer-reviewed studies on academic achievement reveal a positive impact of Homeschooling, but a few studies show a negative effect of Homeschooling. In this study, the main objective is to find the implications of Homeschooling on the achievement of students and finding benefits of Homeschooling. The method used in the study is the analysis of published literature, use from the database available in free open source resources and websites. The present research on the achievements of students who are homeschool will be useful to the parents and policymakers in finding the benefits, policy framing, and advantages of Homeschooling over traditional schooling.

Keywords: Homeschooling, Traditional Schooling, Online Education,

1. Introduction

In India, "The Right of Children to Free and Compulsory Education (RTE) Act," envisaged in the Article 21-A, was passed in the year 2009. According to (Department of School Education and Literacy, Ministry of Human Resource Development, 2018), Homeschooling means that every child has a right to get free and compulsory full-time elementary education of satisfactory and equal quality in a formal school satisfying norms and standards laid by the Government. In the Act, it mentions that schooling of a child between age 6 to 14 is mandatory, and the education should be complete from the formal school, thus it doesn't clarify the legitimacy of Homeschooling and its consequences. The Government of India, has not taken any action on parents for Homeschooling nor made Homeschooling illegal, instead it states, (As cited "Is homeschooling legal in India? | Homeschooling India," n.d.), "the parents who are not satisfied with the curriculum and syllabus followed by the school may follow the homeschooling approach. These children on reaching a class 10 may opt for board exams conducted by the National Open Schooling or International General Certificate of Secondary Education".

Further, the article (As cited "Is homeschooling legal in India? | Homeschooling India," n.d.), says that Government has retracted from the rule of legalizing Homeschooling admitting in the court that the "RTE does not legalize homeschooling." The Government is in a dilemma about Homeschooling of children, (Mahak Arora, 2018), urges that Government legally prohibits Homeschooling, it does not interfere or act against the parents. The Government allows parents who wish to does not want to admit their children in formal school instead wants home teaching (Mahak Arora, 2018). (As cited in Chinki Sinha, 2016), to get rid of artificial an oppressive formal schooling, Manish Jain from Udaipur has launched the ShikshantarAndolan. In the year he co-founded Swaraj University, which dedicates to self-designed learning for the students and based on the green entrepreneurship.

What is Homeschooling?

The education imparted through formal, non-formal, and informal education system. In the informal education system, parents in their home provide training to the children. The Universalization of education and the industrial revolution has shifted the role of educating their children from home to school. But recently, with the advent of homeschooling education, the role of education has come back home due to higher education among parents and learning according to the needs and pace of the students. According to (Mahak Arora, 2018), the higher literacy rates among parents has brought momentum in the Homeschooling of children the parents teach their children at their home according to the abilities of their children. Thus Homeschooling is teaching children at their home instead of sending them to any formal education system. According to (Patrick Farenga, n.d.), Homeschooling is an educational method where education is imparted at home rather than in the institution designed for giving knowledge to the students. According to (Brian D. Ray, n.d.), Homeschooling, is an education based on the instruction provided by the parent to their children at home, it a form of education where parents are responsible for designing learning, planning and executing the instructions. In Homeschooling, parents are responsible for developing curriculum, determining learning objectives, and pedagogical approaches. Further (Brian D. Ray, n.d.) elaborates that the Homeschooling not based on the education providers such as state, institute, and organization instead it is based on the experiences given at home and also occurs in libraries, science exhibitions, fields, forests, shops, art centres, gardens, gymnasium, and sports grounds. (What Is Homeschool? - FamilyEducation," n.d.), presents the concept of Homeschooling as the total responsibility of educating the children lies on the parents rather than transferring this responsibility to the public or private institutions.

Objective

The objective of this review of literature is to find (Baig, 2019);

- The impact of Homeschooling on student's achievements.

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- The benefits of Homeschooling
- The advantages of Homeschooling over traditional schooling.

2. Method

In this study, the peer-reviewed literature analyzes by using the database from free open source resources and websites. The directories used in the study to analyses impact of Homeschooling on the achievement of students are Google Search Engine, Social Science Research Network (SSRN), Google Scholar and Directory of Open Educational Research (DOAJ). The keywords used in the search engines and directories are "Impact of homeschooling," "Achievement of homeschooled students," "Achievement of formal school students," and "Advantages of homeschooling."

3. Literature Review

The research findings by(Snyder, 2018), shows that there is statistical significance in the mathematics and science subtests of students. The analysis indicates that the students who educated from the homeschooling approach academically prepared for the college as the traditionally schooled students. As (Ray, 2010), the study revealed that the achievements in test scores are exceptionally high for the students who Educated through homeschooling approach. The result shows that the mean scores in the achievement test of homeschooling students for every subtest (minimum of 80th percentile) are more than those of students from traditional schools.

Further (Ray, 2010), reveals that there are no statistically significant differences in achievement by whether the student has been educated whole life through Homeschooling, whether the student is admitted in school with a structured curriculum and the degree of control of state on Homeschooling through rules and regulations. In the study, Calvery(As cited in Rudner, 1999) found that students achievement from Arkansas homeschooled of grades 4,7 and ten is better than the accomplishment of public schooled. The results show that students who homeschooled scored better than the students from the public school for grade 10 in science, social science, mathematics, and reading. In homeschooling student's abilities in the study skills, critical thinking, self-reliance, and love for learning can develop. The results from the study by (Rudner, 1999), show that the parents of homeschool students have more formal education than the parents in the general population. The achievement test score among the homeschool is exceptionally higher than the scores of students from public schools.

Further, the students have completed their entire education from Homeschooling have a higher level of academic achievement than the students from traditional schools. The Charlotte Mason method mostly used in the Homeschooling, (As cited Snyder, 2011), developed by the British educator Charlotte Mason, the emphasis that children should educate as a complete person using the "living books" or "books having a real life like characters."

Further, Mason elaborates that (As cited in Snyder, 2011), students education is through life and not by the dry facts available in the textbook. In their study (As cited in Martin-Chang, Gould, & Meuse, 2011), observe that the students who educated from the structured Homeschooling were found to be superior to the students who taught from the traditional school. The statistical analysis MANOVA suggests that the standardized achievement between the students of Homeschooling and conventional schooling is significantly different, and it is in favour of Homeschooling (Martin-Chang, Gould, & Meuse, 2011). (Watson, 2019) Discuss the variation in the results obtained through Homeschooling due to methods adopted in the teaching of students at home. According to Ray (2004), (as cited in Watson, 2019), in the Homeschooling there is flexibility in events and studies like assisting in community work, internship, tour, excursions, household work, travelling, gardening, and competitive exams.

Further, in the study, it observed that the home school education usually focuses on developing skills in reading, writing, mathematics, and science. As (Moreau, 2012), has noted that when the students form homeschooled, and the traditional school s compared with Stanford Achievement Test then results in shoes that the students who are homeschool have scored above the median in the test areas of math, science, and verbal skills. Davis, in his study (As cited in Moreau, 2012) discuss that those students who e homeschooled achieved 30-37 per cent of higher scores than their public school peers. In subjects such as reading, writing, language, fine arts, math, science, and social sciences, the homeschooled students were performing higher than the traditionally schooled children in every grade. (Moreau, 2012), has noted that in the Homeschooling there is flexibility in the content, methods, and place for education, in the homeschool learning is possible at any time and any place without any formality or rules and regulations. The success of the homeschool mostly depends on the factor that parents have a better emotional attachment and have a good understanding of their children. (Ray, 2017), provides information concerning Homeschooling of black children, the performance of black children who are homeschool is significantly better than the performance of the black public school in the areas of reading, language, math, social studies, and science. The researchers' Martin-Chang, Gould, & Meuse, 2011, (As cited in Ray, 2017), have found that the students from structured homeschool environment scores higher than their traditional counterparts while the students from unstructured homeschooling environment scores lower than the institutional school students.

The analysis of findings from the review suggests that the achievement of students from Homeschooling is better than their counterparts, but there are exceptions. (Moreau, 2012), in his findings says that the parents who take out their children from the traditional schools because of the belief, religion, better academic opportunities or disbelief in the conventional education system are not to be found thriving in the homeschooling education system. (Rudner, 1999), contend that there is a limitation in Homeschooling, the homeschools impart necessary skills in science, mathematics, reading, and social studies, but they lack the scope, sequence, and emphasis, in giving education, in Homeschooling the

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main focus is on religious and moral values. In their study, Aram, Meidan, and Deitcher (2016), (As cited in Ray, 2017), on traditional and homeschool of Kindergarten students of conventional schools were found to be significantly better in the knowledge of letter and name writing than the homeschool students further there is no significant difference between them in terms of phonological awareness. Qaish (2007), contend that (As cited in Ray, 2017), the achievement in math of traditional schooling students is found to be slightly higher than the home educated students, this results may occur due to different types of teaching & learning materials used in teaching students of Homeschooling and traditional schooling and various kinds of interaction used in the teaching-learning process.

4. Conclusions

The analysis of the literature review revealed that the achievements of students who are homeschool are significantly higher than the performance of their peer students from traditional schooling. The mean score in the achievement test of Homeschooling is higher than the students from regular school. The findings from various suggest that homeschooling students have better opportunities in developing skills in reading, creative thinking, independent thinking, self-learning, and self-reliance. Few studies suggest the lower achievement in the test scores among students who homeschool. This finding support by the survey by Aram, Meidan, and Deitcher (2016), (As cited in Ray, 2017), on conventional schooling and Homeschooling of Kindergarten students, the study regarding knowledge of letter and name writing were found to be significantly higher in the traditional school students.

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